

**DETERMINATION OF THE SALT TOLERANCE INDEX
(STI) OF WHEAT (TRITICUM AESTIVUM L).****Olimjonova Sadokat Gulomjon kizi
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sadokat102030@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19567649>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 09th April 2026Accepted: 11th April 2026Online: 13th April 2026**KEYWORDS***Soft wheat, salt tolerance, viability, NaCl, genotype***ABSTRACT**

The salt tolerance index of wheat varieties is determined by a number of indicators, including the viability and morphometric indicators of the blades under salinity conditions, as well as their ability to maintain high germination energy and strength in a saline environment. This index is not a single numerical indicator, but together allows us to identify the genotypes most adapted to soil salinity conditions. Among the studied wheat varieties, the highest STI value was observed in Pakhlavon (85.58%), followed by Es-4 (80.88%) and Kairaktosh (80.62%), and the lowest STI values were observed in Ezos (64.83%) and Es-1 (67.98%).

Wheat is an important cereal grain consumed by one-third of the world's population and is a major source of carbohydrates, proteins, and minerals in the daily diet. In recent years, the intensification of climate change has had a significant impact on yield and quality, as various abiotic stresses, including drought, salinity, and flooding, occur in unpredictable ways. Today, the tolerance of wheat to salinity is one of the most pressing problems worldwide. According to scientists, soil salinity has affected more than 20% of all cultivated areas in the world [1, 4].

Ibrahimova et al. studied the responses to osmotic and oxidative stress in salt-tolerant and salt-sensitive wheat genotypes and found that when treated with 150 mmol NaCl, the relative water content and osmotic potential in leaves of salt-sensitive genotypes decreased significantly compared to salt-tolerant genotypes. [2]

Sun et al. reported that long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs) are increasingly recognized as cis- and trans-regulators of protein-coding genes in plants, especially in response to abiotic stressors. The authors also noted that salt-responsive lncRNA target genes showed strong correlations with various plant defense mechanisms, such as signal transduction, transcriptional regulation, ion homeostasis, osmoregulation, reactive oxygen species harvesting, photosynthesis, phytohormone regulation, and kinase activity. Similarly, another study investigating the effects of salt stress on plant morphology, physiology, and mRNA expression in different wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) cultivars showed that ROS-neutralizing genes (TaSOD6, TaCAT1/5/6, TaPOD7, TaP5CS1) were found to have higher expression levels than salt-sensitive genes (TaDREB3, TaWRKY19, TaERF5a, TaLTP1, TaTIP2) [3].

Determination of salt tolerance index (STI). The salt tolerance index of wheat varieties is determined by a number of indicators, including the viability of shoots under salinity conditions and morphometric indicators, as well as their ability to maintain high germination

energy and strength in a saline environment. This index is not a single numerical indicator, but together it allows us to identify the most adapted genotypes under soil salinity conditions.

Table 1 presents data on the salt tolerance indices of soft wheat varieties. Based on the data in the table, the highest STI value among the studied wheat varieties was observed in Pakhlavon (85.58%), followed by Es-4 (80.88%) and Kairaktash (80.62%), and the lowest STI values were observed in Ezoz (64.83%) and Es-1 (67.98%) varieties.

Table 1

Effect of different salt concentrations on salt tolerance index in common wheat cultivars

Varieties	Treatment				
	Control (T ₀)	50 mM NaCl (T ₁)	100 mM NaCl (T ₂)	150 mM NaCl (T ₃)	Average(G)
T					
V					
Bardosh	100.00	72.64	68.13	59.45	75.06
Kayraktash	100.00	83.21	76.45	62.82	80.62
Paxlavon	100.00	85.72	84.07	72.58	85.58
Ezoz	100.00	53.81	58.87	46.63	64.83
Ok marvarid	100.00	73.10	68.15	56.24	74.37
Es-1	100.00	70.62	56.74	44.54	67.98
Es-4	100.00	82.78	78.24	62.48	80.88
Es-7	100.00	65.18	58.76	40.70	72.79
Es-61	100.00	82.76	77.24	58.89	79.72
Average (X)	100.00	74.42	69.63	56.04	
	S. E _m ±	HCP ₀₅	CV, %		
V	1.22	3.64			
T	0.73	2.23	4.89		
V x T	2.64	6.52			

Note: V – variety, T– treatment, V x T – interaction between variety and treatment, X – average, mx – average arithmetic error, CV – coefficient of variation.

The results of the conducted study confirm that as the level of salt stress increases, the salt tolerance of varieties decreases. For example, when treated with 150 mM NaCl (T3 variant), the STI index changed from 72.58% (Pakhlavon) to 44.54% (Es-1). However, this indicator is significantly reduced in all studied varieties when cultivated in 150 mM NaCl solution compared to the control. Thus, based on STI data, the varieties Pakhlavon, Kayraktash, Es-4 and Es-61 were determined to be highly tolerant, while Ezos, Es-1, Es-7, Ok Marvarid and Bardosh were determined to be moderately tolerant.

The results of the conducted studies showed that a decrease in the salt tolerance index of the varieties leads to a significant change in the relative water content in the leaves and the membrane stability index. The results of the correlation analysis show that the salt tolerance index is significantly and positively correlated with the relative water content in the leaves and the membrane stability index.

Conclusion. The salt tolerance index can be used to evaluate wheat genotypes under NaCl stress. The level of tolerance showed that NaCl stress of 150 mM and above has a lethal effect on wheat at the germination stage.

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